

FREEDOM AND RESPONSIBILITY ARE HARMONIZED BY MAN AND SOCIETY IMPORTANCE IN DEVELOPMENT

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ANNOTATION. The article talks about the emergence of the concepts of freedom and responsibility in society, its development and the factors affecting it. Freedom and responsibility are analyzed as a category of social and humanitarian sciences.

KEY WORDS: Freedom, responsibility, right, duty, society, social life, need, interest.

Human rights and freedoms are the highest value. It should be noted that human rights are the basis of human existence and coexistence, and they are common and inalienable for all. According to the philosophers of ancient antiquity, natural rights depend on nature, and people differ from each other when they are born. Moreover, striving to bring out this natural right and freedom, to be able to provide one's needs and security only together, led to the socialization and activation of a person.

In a narrow sense, the concept of human rights and freedoms includes only the rights protected by the state, and it is not an easy task to limit them by constitutional legal bases or state borders. These rights include the equality of all citizens before the law, the right to life and physical integrity, respect for human dignity, freedom from arbitrary and illegal arrest or detention, freedom of conscience and religion, the rights of parents to raise their children, and resistance to oppression. including the right to do and others. Human rights in a broad sense represent the general freedom of a person.

Every person, regardless of nationality, race, social status, should be equal to another person and all people in society should have equal rights, especially in the field that directly affects people's lives, i.e. employees of state bodies, leaders and ordinary people. civil rights should be equal but professional rights and

responsibilities should be greater. Because these civil servants are persons who protect people's well-being and rights and ensure social equality of people.

"What gives human rights real strength is their universality. It crosses any borders, overcomes any obstacles. The struggle for human rights has always been a struggle against dictatorship and all forms of injustice: slavery, dependence, violent colonialism. Today, its relevance has not decreased or its essence has not changed" [1].

The need to protect human freedoms and rights arose in the context of the struggle against the authoritarian medieval system. An ordinary person, his dignity, honor, pride and, most importantly, his life, were criticized in the medieval legal rules, humanism and the fact that every person is equal before God. therefore, he put forward the ideas that he should have equal rights before the laws of the society. It appeared during the Renaissance and Enlightenment. These ideas began to spread in the Eastern nations during the colonial period. In the new era, colonialism and world wars gave socio-political and economic meaning to the issue of freedom and responsibility. As an example, it can be said that the colonial policy of Great Britain, Tsarist Russia, France and other countries, or the two terrible world wars that shook the people of the whole world, made the ideas of human dignity, freedom and responsibility, their emergence and implementation even more important. actualizes. Just take the Second World War, how many people were brutally killed by Nazi Germany in a variety of very heinous ways. Various experiments were conducted on them.

In such abominable situations and at a time when people's rights and freedoms are not protected, the positive development and progress of societies has stopped. However, there will be positive growth and development in a society where people's rights and freedoms are protected. A person can show his potential as an individual only if he has sufficient rights and freedoms and certain obligations. This, in turn, paves the way for the development of society. If the

society is based on a totalitarian structure, and as we mentioned above, people are deprived of their right to freedom, or are subjected to various pressures, then people in such a society cannot take bold steps towards their aspirations, interests, and goals while living in fear. In such a society, people cannot openly show their abilities. When a country establishes its sovereignty over another country, it first limits the rights and freedoms of the citizens of the dependent country to a certain extent.

Even during the Soviet era, the Uzbek people experienced such disappointments. During the Soviet era, human rights and freedoms were violated to a certain extent. The CPSU implemented a policy of discrimination against farmers and agricultural workers in particular. "Complete alienation of the producer from his products and in general from ownership, excessive nationalization of social life, flatness in distribution, economy and life based on lack of production and other shortcomings caused a lot of damage to social consciousness and human relations. The Soviet totalitarian system deeply deformed society and human consciousness, worldview, moral and aesthetic values, mental and emotional environment, attitude to life, and spirituality in general" [2]. During the Soviet era, people's rights were violated and injustice prevailed. During Tsarist Russia and the Soviet regime, the most educated, socially active, literate layer of the population was wiped out or forced to flee to foreign countries. During Stalin's era, the policy of "Stalin's repressors", the policy of "Uzbeks' work", and their imprisoning people on false charges made people poor, neglected the society, and demanded their rights. increased the number of people who do not get it. Because after bringing the society's citizens to this state, it became very easy to deprive them of their spirituality and culture.

A society that does not know its spirituality, culture, values and history will have no future. Such a people will gradually be absorbed into a self-governing people. The first President Islam Karimov was shocked by this and set himself the

goal of making the dreams and hopes of the Uzbek people come true, the Uzbek people living in a free democratic society and re-developing the society, and this goal was achieved in 1991. it turned out. On August 31 of this year, Uzbekistan was declared an independent democratic state. Independence opened the door to great opportunities for people. Human rights and freedoms were put first and this was reinforced by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan, as a sovereign, democratic, legal and secular state, devotes more than a third of its Constitution to the issue of human rights and freedoms and their protection. Constitutionally strengthened their primacy and abolished the principle of priority of state interests over human rights[3].

The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the strengthening of human rights and freedoms has been consistently developing, the country's commitment to human rights has found its constitutional expression, and today a broad legislative base has been created in this field. The important thing is that the decisive factors for the further strengthening and development of human rights and freedoms in Uzbekistan, including people's power and the state's responsibility to people, have been determined. As a result, it paved the way for the social development of the society. The spirit of patriotism and humanitarianism was formed in people. People were given freedom of conscience, freedom of speech, freedom of thought. People began to move freely in the state. Now, instead of irresponsible people living in the tribe of "if you give, I will eat, if you hit me, I will die", now there are more free-thinking, responsible citizens who feel that they are responsible for society, contribute to the development of society.

In his speech at the eleventh session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov said: "The root of the changes in our life is the spiritual awakening of our people. The fact that the ancient rights of our mother tongue have been

restored, the real Uzbek traditions are taking place in life, and the fact that our values are finding their place also has a positive effect on people's mood. Uzbek began to believe in himself" [4] and said that "Human rights and democracy are fully compatible with the national and state interests of Uzbekistan, the national way of thinking and mentality of the people" [6] the democratic, humane, just civil society taking a strong place in our country and the real, broad human rights and freedoms implemented in it can be witnessed.

The responsibility of the individual and the society is an integral sign of the legal state. In a non-democratic state, only the citizen's responsibility to the state is recognized. It is as if he gives rights and freedom to a citizen and assigns his status. In the legal state, we see a different picture. Here, attention is paid to the responsibility of state bodies and officials to citizens for their rights and freedoms. This responsibility acquires a practical meaning only in the conditions of the existence of relevant regulatory and legal documents, which ensure that officials guilty of violating the rights and freedoms of citizens are held accountable and provide for taking drastic measures.

Human rights are a principle according to which "all people are born free"¹. The fact that all people are born free and have the right to freedom means that everyone is free to choose their own way of life and think. This freedom is limited by respect for the freedom of others. In a society consisting of free people, it is necessary to have a well-formed sense of responsibility for people, mutual respect, indifference to the freedom of others. Indeed, the good development of society depends on free-thinking, responsible, active citizens with a high legal culture and spirituality.

After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan expanded real democracy in social and state construction in every way and set the main goal of entering the ranks of developed and enlightened countries, not only expressing human freedom, democratic rights and freedoms of citizens in constitutional laws,

but also its development and improvement. For this purpose, the state bodies, public organizations, which are being created, are implementing and guaranteeing it with the multifaceted activities they are conducting" [6].

Human rights are a common achievement of the historical development of mankind, but they are becoming one of the urgent problems of the world community today. Because the free development of peoples and nations and human rights are being violated due to the existence of totalitarian regimes and the disasters of war. Franklin Delano Roosevelt, one of the former Presidents of the United States, supported the four freedoms and said in his speech on January 6, 1941: "Liberty means that human rights prevail everywhere and in everything. We support all those who are fighting for these rights or for them" [6].

One of the conditions for the democratization of any state that aims to build a democratic civil society is the full definition of human rights and freedoms in laws and the creation of conditions for their provision. The main goal of building a democratic legal state of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to fully ensure the rights and freedoms of every citizen living in this country" [7]. Today, Uzbekistan is a component of the world community and an equal subject with full rights. It recognizes the UN Charter, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenants on Civil and Political Rights and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, participates in the agreements of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, and many international conventions.

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